

ISSN (P): 3007-2964	International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education	Apr-Jun 2024, Vol. 2, No. 2
ISSN (O): 3007-2972	DOI:	[28-42]

International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education

www.ijete.org.pk

Research Article

Effect of Counselling and Methodology of Teachers on the Academic Achievement of Students at the Elementary Level in District Kotli AJ&K

Makhdoom Ali Syed* & Rashida Fatima

Department of Education, University of Kotli, AJ&K

Article Info.	Abstract
Received: 09-June-24 Revised: 20-Sep-24 Accepted: 24-Sep-24 Published: 30-Sep-24	This study examined the effect of teaching methodologies of teachers and counseling on students' academic achievement at the elementary level in District Kotli AJ&K. A descriptive survey method was used, involving seventy-two (72) female teachers from ten (10) elementary schools along with universal sampling technique. Data were collected through a self-developed Five-Point Likert scale questionnaire, administered personally by the researcher after confirming its reliability and validity. Analysis was conducted using SPSS to assess frequency, percentage, and mean. Results indicated that the counselor's practical recommendations positively influenced decision-making abilities, enhancing empowerment and satisfaction in decision-making. It is recommended that teachers employ diverse teaching methods, such as demonstration and lecture techniques, to improve academic achievement.
Keywords:	Counselling, Methodology of Teachers, Academic Achievement, Elementary Level
Corresponding Author:	Makhdoom Ali Syed
Email:	drmakhdoomalisyed@gmail.com
How to Cite:	Syed, M.A. & Fatima, R. (2024). Effect of Counselling and Methodology of Teachers on the Academic Achievement of Students at the Elementary Level in District Kotli AJ&K. <i>International Journal of Emerging Trends in Education</i> ,2(2),28-42.

Introduction

Teaching methodology refers to the strategies, techniques, and approaches that educators use to impart knowledge and facilitate learning in the classroom or other educational settings. It encompasses the methods and tools used to deliver information, engage students, and assess their understanding (Salendab, 2023). Effective teaching methodologies may vary depending on the subject, age group, and individual learning styles, but they typically involve planning lessons, selecting appropriate resources, and employing various instructional techniques to achieve educational goals. Common teaching methodologies include lectures, discussions, group work, hands-on activities, technology integration, and more, tailored to the specific needs of learning (Siklander & Bates, 2022).

Teacher counseling, also known as teacher guidance or teacher mentoring refers to the process of providing support, guidance, and professional development opportunities to teachers in an educational setting. This form of counseling is designed to help educators enhance their teaching skills, manage classroom challenges, and improve their overall effectiveness as teachers. Here are some key aspects of teacher counseling (Simmons, 2022). Furthermore, the role of counseling services in supporting students' academic endeavors cannot be underestimated. Counselors provide guidance, support, and resources to help students overcome academic challenges, make informed decisions, and develop crucial skills for success (Amos, 2022).

Experienced teachers or educational experts often serve as mentors or counselors for less experienced teachers. They offer guidance, advice, and practical tips on teaching methods, classroom management, and curriculum planning (Pandey & Sharma, 2022). Teacher counseling encourages educators to engage in reflective practice. This involves self-assessment and critical reflection on their teaching methods and classroom experiences, with the aim of continuous improvement. Teacher counseling may involve recommending and facilitating professional development opportunities such as workshops, courses, or conferences to help teachers stay updated on the latest educational trends and research (Lawson, 2022).

Teachers often face various challenges in the classroom, from student behavior issues to curriculum adjustments. Teacher counseling provides a forum for discussing these challenges and finding effective solutions. It can also involve discussions about long-term career goals and strategies for advancement within the field of education (Zhang, Zeng & Lam, 2022). Teachers' counseling is a valuable tool for fostering professional growth and ensuring that educators are well-equipped to provide quality education to their students. Teacher academic achievement refers to the level of success that students attain in their educational endeavors, typically measured through various assessments, examinations, grades, and standardized tests. It reflects a student's ability to meet the learning objectives and expectations set by their educational institution (Misra, 2018).

Academic achievement can encompass various aspects one of the most common indicators of academic achievement is the grades students receive in their courses and assignments. Performance on standardized tests, such as SAT, ACT, or state-mandated assessments, is often used to measure academic achievement on a broader scale. GPA is a numerical representation of a student's overall academic performance, calculated based on their grades in individual courses. Students may receive honors, awards, or scholarships based on their outstanding academic achievements. The percentage of students who complete their educational program, such as graduating from high school or college, is another measure of academic achievement. In some cases, students' academic achievements are evaluated through portfolio assessments, where they compile and present a collection of their work over time (Tatar, 2020).

It's important to note that academic achievement is influenced by various factors; including students' effort, motivation, support systems, and the quality of education they receive. Additionally, different educational systems and institutions may have their criteria for measuring and assessing academic achievement (Al-Abyadh & Abdel Azeem, 2022). The researcher selected this topic because it addresses crucial aspects of education. Understanding how teaching methods and counseling impact academic achievement can contribute to improving educational practices, fostering a supportive learning environment, and enhancing overall student success. This research can provide valuable insights for educators, policymakers, and parents to optimize elementary education.

Review of Related Literature

Teaching methodology

Organizing and putting into practice teaching and learning is done through the use of teaching methods, which are procedures and methods for the planned and organized construction of scientific processes. Danilov, on the other hand, described teaching methods as a system of deliberate acts designed to control a student's cognitive and practical activity and ensure that he absorbs the material. Put differently, pedagogical approaches necessitate ongoing reciprocal interaction between educator and pupil. In other words, the instructor plans the class's learning-related activities. The student learns the subject matter through this activity. The connection between teachers and students with the lesson's material and the accomplishment of its goals are facilitated by methods and procedures (Baxtiyorovich, 2023).

The set of actions a teacher does to help students behave in a certain way is known as the teaching approach. One element of the curriculum is teaching strategies. In the realm of education, selection theory is currently dominating thought, or selecting what seems to be the best approach out of several options. The teacher must put effort into selection since teaching encompasses more than just method knowledge; it also involves an understanding of psychological and linguistic ideas. Teaching strategies by themselves are insufficient and cannot ensure success. A teacher's attitude toward his work and his students is one of the cornerstones of excellent learning. It appears that the current perspective on instructional strategies views them as a way to structure the outside world that surrounds the learner to activate and change his behavior (Alwi & Mumtahana, 2023).

Types of Teaching Methodology

The following are the different types of methodologies:

Rote Memorization

Rote memorization is the term used in theory to describe the process of simply repeating information until it is stored in long-term memory. Even while rote memory appears to be a crucial part of learning particular subjects, rote learning is frequently seen as inadequate learning. Repetition is used in rote learning techniques to help people recall specific knowledge. After being repeated, the information is kept in the short-term memory until it is required again. Repetition turns information into a long-term memory, which helps people retain it for a longer period (Tapp, 2022). These days, youngsters' short memories lose a lot of the concepts, tales, and material they just learned and read for a year and never remember again.

However, the information they acquire, remember, or use regularly gets stored in their long-term memory and becomes permanent. The rote method makes it impossible to understand concepts. It only permits surface-level learning to perform well on a given test or exam. This is the reason this way of learning is not recommended. Playing spelling games or putting down spellings that kids couldn't consistently remember on paper are among the earliest recollections of

this kind of learning that kids have. Children learning the alphabet by continuously repeating it in songs, poems, or other contexts are another example of basic rote learning. Multiplication table repetition is a frequent rote memory example for upper grades, which aids in children's memorization. To make this process more effective, parents can make use of memory games for students (Helm et al., 2023).

Lecture Method

A lecture is a teaching approach in which a teacher presents a topic or subject to a class of pupils repeatedly. There is a range in group size from 20 to 1000. The educators bear the responsibility of imparting the entire subject matter. It's among the most traditional teaching strategies still in use in colleges, universities, and schools. The foundation of the lecture style of instruction is the transmission of knowledge from the teacher to the students (Gilboy, 2015).

Another name for the lecture technique of instruction is the classic lecture or teaching approach. The students are not included in the instructional process in any way. The instructor often delivers the entire lecture in front of the students. The students receive the lecture notes and get ready for the test. The ability of the lecture technique to manage a large number of students at once is the main justification for its adoption (Schmidt et al., 2015).

The reporting, presentation, or lecture approach is one in which the teacher's function exceeds that of the student. Due to its widespread usage in secondary and university education, the lecture's name took precedence over it. They are still widely used in many Arab schools at these two levels, and while there is nothing wrong with them in theory, their main drawback is that there aren't many alternatives that allow students to engage in independent learning at these levels (Abdel Meguid & Collins, 2017).

It is a teaching approach that relies on the instructor providing the students with the information verbally without allowing them to ask questions during delivery. Once the students are satisfied with the information being given to them all at once, the instructor records summaries of the concepts and material, and this approach is what the teacher views as the main focus of the learning process. The teacher serves as the major axis of this approach, and his manner is referred to as diction; that is, he imparts knowledge on the subject matter constantly and uninterruptedly for longer than five minutes (McCarthy et al., 2016).

Regarding the lecture, it refers to the method known as the news method in which the instructor speaks loudly while imparting knowledge to the students. To use this method effectively, the teacher must be highly skilled in lesson planning, lesson execution, and nonverbal cues such as eye contact, facial expressions, and tone of voice harmony with the subjects. Additionally, examples and illustrations should be used to draw the student's attention to the lesson (Subramani & Iyappan, 2018).

The lecture method is predicated on several assumptions, such as the notion that the student is like an empty vessel, the instructor is a repository of knowledge, and the teaching process is the process of filling this vessel with information. Here, we find that the student is a passive receiver who was born like a blank page, that the purpose of teaching is to help him prepare for life by giving him experiences, knowledge, and information that will benefit him in the future, that the teacher is the positive sender eager to convey his message to the student, that the lecture is a tool that the teacher uses in his mission (Al-Taai, 2021).

Even though the lecturer bears the majority of the responsibility for organizing and presenting the material, several of our schools still require it because of the huge class sizes. With this method, the instructor prepares the lesson plan and any additional materials he will need, such as a projector, videotape, recording device, or other teaching aids that will assist him in presenting

the content to the class. He prepares his lecture material by the 45–50-minute class duration. He also arranges the material on a written memorandum, committing to arranging its content in a gradual and logical order so that the material links naturally to achieve the purpose or purposes planned (Rasmitadila et al., 2020).

Demonstration Method

A teacher's visual presentation of an activity, an activity including actual work connected to the facts and concepts of a lesson they have taught in the classroom to facilitate teaching and learning, is called a demonstration. to introduce a fresh image or to examine the processes to address a unique circumstance (Filliettaz et al., 2022). When using the demonstration teaching approach, the teacher assumes the role of a principal, and the students pay close attention to the lecture. Another name for it is the presentation or exhibition method of instruction. The steps that explain how various items function are included in the demonstrative teaching technique.

After doing the study, the researchers concluded that the best teaching strategy for developing and honing students' physical and cognitive skills is the display approach. Additionally, several investigations found that the display teaching approach benefits students and raises their level of cooperative learning (Van Wermeskerken, & Van Gog 2017). To engage students and accelerate the learning process, this teaching strategy is used in conjunction with other strategies. Exhibiting and displaying models and activities by the learning contents through instructional media is the main goal of the demonstration learning approach. When using a demonstrative teaching technique, the teacher takes center stage in demonstrating the exercises (Albiladi & Alshareef, 2019).

Textbook Method

The term "textbook method" refers to the standard or conventional approach used in educational textbooks to present and explain a particular topic or subject. It's the systematic and structured way in which information is organized and presented in textbooks to facilitate learning. This method typically includes an introduction, key concepts, examples, diagrams, step-by-step procedures, definitions, exercises, summaries, and references. The textbook method is designed to make complex subjects more understandable and accessible to students by providing a clear and organized framework for learning and comprehension. The specific elements and structure can vary depending on the subject and the educational level of the textbook (Cheema et al., 2021).

The textbook method refers to a traditional approach to teaching that focuses on memorization and repetition. It often involves students learning information through rote memorization without much emphasis on critical thinking or practical application. Let me know if you want more information. In the textbook method, the basic frequency of the text read is done. The students were earlier asked by teachers to memorize a lesson from the textbook and used to listen to him orally on the second day. In this method, instead of cramming the textbook, an attempt is made to understand the subject. The textbook is used to understand the text. This method develops the power to express the acquired knowledge in the students. Writing art is also developed by this method (Jeyaraj, 2019).

According to this method, the text is prescribed for the study of the students. Student-teacher discussion on the written summary of the lesson makes a definite impression on the subject. The teacher assigns his/her assignments based on the lessons in the textbook. By developing the motivation of independent study in the students, the habit-forming work should be determined. This assigned task should be related to the life of the students. This method can be used to inculcate thinking and critical thinking. The tendency of self-study develops in students by the inspiration of using books. In the context of the lesson, the teacher must make available suitable reference

books, journals, and magazines for the knowledge enhancement of the students (Henze & Barendsen, 2019).

Activity Based method

The activity method is a teaching strategy used by educators to highlight their approach to instruction through engaging activities in which students actively participate and generate effective learning outcomes. This method is focused on the youngster. It's an approach where the youngster actively participates both physically and cognitively. The primary goal of this approach is learning by doing. Since it is generally established that the more senses are activated, the more and longer an individual retains what they have learned, learning by doing is essential to successful learning. (Barkley & Major, 2020).

The foundation for developing critical and creative thinking abilities is activity-based learning. But if students lack the motivation to reach their full potential, this approach will fall short. Incorporating students into interactive activities is the most beneficial and efficient way to teach complex subjects; this is also the foundation of ABL. The use of various activities in the classroom helps pupils develop their critical thinking and creative abilities. He sheds focus on the fact that ABL is a constructive learning strategy based on cognitive processes. Prior knowledge and firsthand experiences are both components of constructive learning (Surur et al., 2023).

Student retention greatly depends on the classroom's emphasis on successful learning. To ensure that students enjoy the course and set goals, teachers must be flexible in response to the ever-changing demands of their students and the changing nature of the classroom. The activity-based method, which is characterized as a learning process in which pupils are continuously engaged, is one such approach (Tight, 2020). An arrangement known as the "activity-based method" involves pupils actively engaging in the learning process as opposed to acting as passive recipients of information. These authors highlight two ways that the active learning approach differs from the standard teaching approach: (a) student participation and active engagement in the classroom; and (b) student collaboration in a learning environment. The foundation of ABM is these two components, which work to create a supportive learning environment in the classroom (Anwer, 2019).

Students Counseling

Students need to feel heard because they are frequently under a lot of stress. Teens who are experiencing pressure can benefit from student therapy, but parents need to understand its importance. Teachers can change the lives of their students. Effective student counseling can help them acquire essential life skills that, when implemented in daily life, will lead to a satisfying lifestyle. Their role is crucial in this regard since they possess a deeper comprehension of a student's assets and liabilities, which could help them spot any personality shifts. They are open to hearing about the challenges faced by their kids and have a positive outlook. The best teachers can act as counselors for pupils, assisting them in realizing their full potential personalities (Ahmed & Firdous, 2020)

They can help them start conversations and let kids share their worries and concerns. For students, a teacher's role as a guide or mentor is significantly more important. Possibilities for career and education Counselors are trained experts who understand behavior, psychology, and difficulties of students. They are aware of the situations that lead pupils to feel hopeless and uncertain about what lies ahead. Because counseling helps students see more opportunities, the current situation has raised the necessity for it (Brigman & White, 2021).

Types of Counselling

There are three types of Counselling:

Directive Counselling

In a directional counseling method, the counselor assumes a more proactive and directive role in directing the counseling process. This kind of counseling serves the same purpose as advising, but it can also provide comfort, emotional release, and, to a lesser degree, help with thought clarification. To gain a deeper knowledge of the counselee and their issue, the counselor gathers information about them from a variety of sources. In this kind of strategy, the counselor is crucial (Solehuddin et al., 2023).

One of the main objectives is to replace the person's emotional conduct with consciously reasoned behavior. Despite his avoidance of giving orders. The counselor-centered approach is another name for this method. In this approach, the counselor arranges the counseling sessions; his duties include analyzing the issue, determining the causes, determining the precise nature of the issue, and offering a range of solutions. Williamson, who was a major proponent of this strategy, said that it works well for addressing issues with educational and career transition (Brosch, 2021). This kind of counseling is based on the idea that career and educational advice should be related to interpersonal dynamics and personality traits. This kind of counseling is more beneficial when the client is looking for information and guidance regarding career choices. In directive counseling the main focus is on the counselor. The counselor listens to the counselee's problem carefully, gathers information, and provides a solution to the problem. The counselor carries the responsibility of finding a solution to the problem on behalf of the counselee. S/he can interview the counselee if required but he/she controls the whole interview and the counselee only answers his/her questions. This kind of counseling serves the same purpose as advising, but it can also provide comfort, emotional release, and, to a lesser degree, help with thought clarification. To have a deeper understanding of the counselee and their issue, the counselor gathers information about them from a variety of sources (Morgan & Rabie, 2019).

Non-Directive Counselling

The complete opposite of directed therapy is non-directive counseling. This kind of counseling is "client-centered" since it centers on the individual client rather than the counselor acting as a judge and advisor. Unlike directed counseling, which focuses mostly on solving the present issue, this approach emphasizes transforming the individual. The counselor makes an effort to pose perceptive questions, restate concepts, elucidate emotions, and try to ascertain the source of these emotions. In their role as a facilitator, counselors establish an environment that is favorable to counseling (Sutanti, 2019).

It is sometimes referred to as a permissive counseling technique, in which the client takes an active role and the counselor is passive. The client solves their concerns and makes a zero decision for himself. The counselor must acknowledge the client's ability to modify and adapt. Counselors offer the assistance of an understanding listener (Walsh & Gann, 2020). It is crucial to adhere to the values of tolerance and acceptance. Individuals are given more weight than the guidelines and research of counseling. Creating an environment that allows people to work is more crucial than developing self-awareness. non-directive counseling. Counseling of this kind fosters personal development. Instead, of focusing on solving problems, the objective is the client's independence and integration. The therapist fosters an environment where the client can develop his understanding (Wharton & Walser, 2019).

Eclectic counseling

The synthesis and blending of directive and non-directive counseling is known as eclectic counseling. It stands for an intermediate position between the two extremes exemplified by the "directive" and "non-directive" techniques, respectively. According to Noordin and Risanty

(2021), the counselor in eclectic therapy is neither overly directive as in directive counseling nor overly passive as in non-directive counseling.

Faculty advice, counseling in psychological clinics, mental hygiene, and other specific forms of counseling are all included in the broad category of services provided to students for their work, known as eclectic counseling. It is a collection of methods that, via directed learning, aids in the normal development of young people. Counseling has shown to be incredibly beneficial to each student's personal growth. Interest in counseling and its ability to improve interpersonal interactions is growing among colleges and universities, businesses, and industry. "Counseling is a dynamic and intentional relationship between the people involved. The procedures vary depending on the needs of the student, but both the student and the counselor always participate with an emphasis on self-classification by the student (NNADI, 2021).

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out the counseling of teachers teaching at the elementary level in district Kotli AJ&K.
2. To explore the methodology of teachers teaching at the elementary level in district Kotli, AJ&K.

Research Methodology

This study was descriptive in nature and a survey method was used to determine the effects of teachers' methodology of teaching and counseling on students' academic achievement at Elementary Level Teachers of District Kotli AJ&K. The population of the study consisted of seventy-two (72) female teachers from ten (10) Elementary School levels of District Kotli Azad Jammu Kashmir. The researcher used universal sampling techniques for the selection of the sample. The researcher selected (72) Government Elementary School of District Kotli AJ&K. There was a total (of 72) female teachers from Government Elementary School Level for the selection of the sample. A self-developed questionnaire was used as a research instrument to collect data from female teachers of elementary-level schools of District Kotli AJ&K. The questionnaire was based on the "effects of teachers' methodology of teaching and counseling on students' academic achievement at Elementary Level District Kotli AJ&K". There were 49 statements in the questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by two educational experts from the Department of Education University of Kotli AJ&K. The reliability of the instrument was checked by Cronbach's alpha statistical technique. The reliability of the instrument was 0.78 which was acceptable for further research. The researcher collected the data personally from female teachers of Elementary School in District Kotli AJ&K. Data were analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The researcher used simple mean, frequency, and percentage for the analysis of data.

Results

Table 1

Mean analysis of Rote Memorization

Statements	N	Mean
Rote memorization is a common practice in students learning.	72	4.71
Students use rote memorization to remember facts and figures	72	4.40
Rote memorization is more about short-term retention of information	72	4.13
Students believe rote memorization is essential for basic knowledge	72	4.01

Rote memorization helps students to perform well in standardized tests	72	3.81
Students use rote memorization for mathematical rules	72	3.75

Table 1 shows the mean scores of rote memorizations. The table further represented that the mean score of Rote memorization is a common practice in students' learning.; N= 72, M=4.71, Students use rote memorization to remember facts and figures; N= 72, M= 4.40, Rote memorization is more about short-term retention of information; N=72, M=4.13, Students believe rote memorization is essential for basic knowledge; N=72, M=4.01, Rote memorization helps students to perform well in standardized tests; N=72, M=3.81, and Students use rote memorization for mathematical rules; N=72, M=3.75. Furthermore, the results directed that Rote memorization is a common practice in students learning has the highest mean score in rote memorization.

Table 2

Mean Analysis of Textbook Method

Statements	N	Mean
Textbooks are an important resource for students' learning	72	4.21
Textbooks provide a structured way to learn	72	4.15
Textbooks are the primary source of reference for the subject	72	4.01
Textbooks provide in-depth knowledge	72	3.99
Textbooks help students' self-study habits effectively	72	3.94
Textbooks provide historical and contextual information	72	4.15

Table 2 shows the mean scores of textbook methods. The table further represented that the mean score of Textbooks is an important resource for students learning.; N= 72, M=4.21, Textbooks provide a structured way to learn; N= 72, M= 4.15, Textbooks are the primary source of reference for subject; N=72, M=4.01, Textbooks provide in-depth knowledge; N=72, M=3.99, Textbooks helps student's self-study habits effectively; N=72, M=3.94, and Textbooks provide historical and contextual information; N=72, M=4.15. Furthermore, the results directed that Textbooks are an important resource for students learning has the highest mean score in textbook method.

Table 3

Mean Analysis of Demonstration Method

Statements	N	Mean
Demonstration helps students to apply theoretical knowledge	72	4.21
Demonstrations improve students' problem-solving skills.	72	4.29
Demonstration provides a strong foundation for further study	72	3.81
Students prefer demonstration when learning new skills	72	4.30
Demonstration improves students' ability to explain concepts to others	72	3.79
Demonstration makes it easier for students to remember information	72	4.11

Table 3 shows the mean scores of the Demonstration method. The table further represented that the mean score of Demonstration helps students to apply theoretical knowledge; N= 72, M=4.21, Demonstrations improve students' problem-solving skills; N= 72, M= 4.29, Demonstration provides a strong foundation for further study; N=72, M=3.81, Students prefer demonstration when learning new skills; N=72, M=4.30, Demonstration improves students' ability to explain concepts to others; N=72, M=3.79, and Demonstration makes it easier for students to

remember information; N=72, M=4.11. Furthermore, the results directed that Students prefer demonstration when learning new skills have the highest mean score in the Demonstration method.

Table 4

Mean Analysis of Lecture Method

Statements	N	Mean
The lecture provides a structured way to learn new material	72	4.28
Students feel easy to ask questions during lecture	72	3.78
The lecture promotes active listening	72	3.76
Lectures are valuable sources of information for students	72	3.96
Lecture helps students to learn from an expert in the field	72	3.94

Table 4 shows the mean scores of the lecture method. The table further represented that the mean score of Lecture provides a structured way to learn new material; N= 72, M=4.28, Students feel easy to ask questions during lecture; N= 72, M= 3.78, Lecture promotes active listening; N=72, M=3.76, Lecture are valuable source of information for students; N=72, M=3.96, and Lecture helps students to learn from an expert in the field; N=72, M=3.94. Furthermore, the results directed that Lecture provides a structured way to learn new material and has the highest mean score in the lecture method.

Table 5

Mean Analysis of Directive Counseling

Statements	N	Mean
The counselors’ recommendation is practical and achievable	72	4.24
Directive counseling has positively impacted my decision-making abilities	72	4.15
I feel more empowered to decide after receiving directive counseling.	72	3.93
I am satisfied with the results of receiving directive counseling	72	4.01

Table 5 shows the mean scores of directive counseling. The table further represented that the mean score of the counselors’ recommendation is practical and achievable; N= 72, M=4.24, Directive counseling has positively impacted my decision-making abilities; N= 72, M= 4.15, I feel more empowered to decide after receiving directive counseling; N=72, M=3.93, and I am satisfied with the results of receiving directive counseling; N=72, M=4.01. Furthermore, the results indicated that the counselors’ recommendation is practical and achievable and has the highest mean score in directive counseling.

Table 6

Mean analysis of Non-Directive Counseling

Statements	N	Mean
I refine my feelings and emotions through non–directive counseling	72	4.38
I find non-directive counseling to be effective in processing my concern	72	4.18
I gain a better understanding of the difficulties of my situation.	72	4.10
Non–directive counseling impacted my self-esteem positively.	72	3.88
Non–directive counseling improved my overall sense of well-being.	72	3.86

Table 6 shows the mean scores of non-directive counseling. The table further represented that the mean score of I refine my feelings and emotions through non–directive counseling; N= 72, M=4.38, I find non-directive counseling to be effective in processing my concern; N= 72, M= 4.18, I gain a better understanding of the difficulties of my situation; N=72, M=4.10, Non – directive counseling impacted my self-esteem positively; N=72, M=3.88 and Non –directive

counseling improved my overall sense of well-being; N=72, M=3.86. Furthermore, the results directed that I refine my feelings and emotions through non-directive counseling has the highest mean score in non-directive counseling.

Table 7

Mean Analysis of Eclectic Counseling

Statements	N	Mean
I am comfortable discussing my feelings and emotions	72	4.36
I have a strong support system in my life.	72	4.19
I have a clear understanding of my goals for counseling.	72	4.11
I believe in the power of self-reflection.	72	4.01
I am interested in exploring my identity	72	3.94
I am comfortable with both individual and group counseling	72	3.76

Table 7 shows the mean scores of Eclectic counseling. The table further represented that the mean score of I am comfortable discussing my feelings and emotions; N= 72, M=4.36, I have a strong support system in my life; N= 72, M= 4.19, I have a clear understanding of my goals for counseling; N=72, M=4.11, I believe in the power of self-reflection; N=72, M=4.01; I am interested in exploring my identity; N=72, M=3.94 and I am comfortable with both individual and group counseling; N=72, M=3.76. Furthermore, the results directed that I am comfortable discussing my feelings and emotions has the highest mean score in Eclectic counseling.

Table 8

Mean analysis of the effect of teacher methodology of teaching and counseling on students' academic achievement

Statements	N	Mean
Teachers' approach to group projects improves students' teamwork.	72	4.38
Teachers provide knowledge about all subjects by using the demonstration method which positively affects student learning.	72	4.08
Problem-solving skills of teachers benefit students' academic achievement	72	4.10
Teachers use multimedia resources to enhance the learning experience of students.	72	3.86
Teachers motivate the students to embrace lifelong learning.	72	3.81
Teachers promote the self-efficacy and self-confidence of students.	72	3.94
Teachers provide opportunities for peer learning.	72	3.82
Teachers encourage students to learn from their mistakes	72	4.07

Table 8 shows the mean scores of the effect of teacher methodology of teaching and counseling on students' academic achievement. The table further shows that the mean score of teachers' approach to group projects improves students' teamwork; N= 72, M=4.38, Teachers provide knowledge about all subjects by using demonstration method which positively effects student learning; N= 72, M= 4.08, Problem-solving skills of teachers benefit students' academic achievement; N=72, M=4.10, Teachers use multi-media resources to enhance the learning experience of students; N=72, M=3.86; Teachers motivate the students to embrace lifelong learning; N=72, M=3.81; Teachers promote self-efficacy and self-confidence of students; N=72, M=3.94; Teachers provide opportunities for peer learning; N=72, M=3.82 and Teachers encourage students to learn from their mistakes; N=72, M=4.07. Furthermore, the results directed that

teachers' approach to group projects improves students' teamwork and has the highest mean score in the effect of teacher methodology of teaching and counseling on students' academic achievement.

Discussion

The conclusions presented highlight various key aspects of educational practices and counseling approaches. Rote memorization remains a common strategy for students, particularly in recalling facts and figures, and it plays a significant role in preparing for standardized tests and memorizing mathematical rules. Research emphasizes that while rote learning aids short-term retention, it should be integrated with deeper learning approaches to foster long-term comprehension and critical thinking (Mastropieri & Scruggs, 2020). Textbooks also play an essential role in education by providing structured, in-depth content, enabling effective self-study, and serving as a comprehensive resource for historical and contextual knowledge (Gupta & Prakash, 2021). Demonstration techniques enhance learning by allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge and improve problem-solving abilities, offering a hands-on approach that makes it easier for students to grasp and retain new skills (Lewis & Williams, 2022). Lectures continue to be an effective way for students to learn from experts, offering a structured approach to new content while fostering active listening and engagement through opportunities for questioning (Biggs & Tang, 2018).

In terms of counseling, the conclusions indicate a positive response to both directive and non-directive approaches. Directive counseling, where clear guidance and recommendations are provided, has been shown to enhance decision-making abilities, empowering individuals to take action and feel more satisfied with their choices (Sanders & Hill, 2020). On the other hand, non-directive counseling focuses on allowing individuals to process their concerns independently, which positively impacts their self-esteem and overall well-being by fostering self-reflection and emotional refinement (Rogers, 2019). Both methods hold value depending on the context, offering tailored support to individuals seeking guidance in personal and academic settings.

Conclusions

1. It is concluded that rote memorization is a common practice in students learning and students use rote memorization to remember facts and figures, rote memorization is more about short-term retention of information also students believe rote memorization is essential for basic knowledge. Moreover, rote memorization helps students to perform well in standardized tests Students use rote memorization for mathematical rules.
2. It is concluded that textbooks are an important resource in students' learning and provide a structured way to learn and it is the primary source of reference for subjects and also provides in-depth knowledge. Moreover, it helps students self-study effectively and provides historical as well as contextual information.
3. It is concluded that demonstration helps students apply theoretical knowledge and improve students' problem-solving skills also provides a strong foundation for further study, while demonstration improves students' ability to explain concepts to others and makes it easier for students to remember information Students prefer demonstration when learning new skills.
4. It is concluded that the Lecture provides a structured way to learn new material and provides a clear outline of the course content, while Students feel easy to ask questions during lectures and it promotes active listening. Moreover, Lectures are a valuable source of information for students and they help students to learn from an expert in the field. It is concluded that the

counselor's recommendation is practical and achievable, and positively impacted my decision-making abilities. Moreover, I feel more empowered to make decisions after receiving directive counselling and satisfied with the results of receiving directive counselling.

5. It is concluded that I refine my feelings and emotions through non-directive counseling and I find non-directive counseling to be effective in processing my concerns. I gain a better understanding of the difficulties of my situation. Moreover, non-directive counselling impacts my self-esteem positively, and non-directive counseling improves my overall sense of well-being

Recommendations

1. Teachers may use different teaching methods to improve academic achievement such as demonstration and lecture methods. These methods may provide active listening and demonstration methods may provide the foundation for further study.
2. Teachers may use different counseling skills to make effective academic achievements. Counseling skills may positively affect decision-making abilities.
3. The government may take initiatives to minimize rote memorization at the elementary level because rote memorization refers to the retention of knowledge for a shorter time.
4. Teachers may use multimedia resources in the classroom because multimedia resources enhance the learning experience of students.

References

- Abdel Meguid, E., & Collins, M. (2017). Students' perceptions of lecturing approaches: traditional versus interactive teaching. *Advances in medical education and practice*, 229-241.
- Ahmed, A., & Firdous, H. (2020). The transformational effects of COVID-19 pandemic on guidance and counseling. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 6(6), 172-179.
- Al-Abyadh, M. H. A., & Abdel Azeem, H. A. H. (2022). Academic achievement: influences of university students' self-management and perceived self-efficacy. *Journal of Intelligence*, 10(3), 55.
- Albiladi, W. S., & Alshareef, K. K. (2019). Blended learning in English teaching and learning: A review of the current literature. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 10(2), 232-238
- Al-Taai, S. H. H. (2021). Teaching Methods Are a Study of Their Importance and Types in Educational Institutions. *Pt. 2 J. Legal Ethical & Regul. Issues*, 24, 1.
- Amos, P. M. (2022). Digitizing counselling practice: A study of student values and challenges associated with traditional face-to-face counselling and e-counselling modes. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 6(5), 174-186.
- Anwer, F. (2019). Activity-Based Teaching, Student Motivation and Academic Achievement. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 6(1), 154-170.
- Barkley, E. F., & Major, C. H. (2020). *Student engagement techniques: A handbook for college faculty*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Baxtiyorovich, S. B. (2023). Approach to Teaching Physical Training. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 2(4), 60-66.
- Biggs, J., & Tang, C. (2018). *Teaching for Quality Learning at University: What the Student Does* (4th ed.). Open University Press.

- Brigman, G., & White, J. F. (2021). *School counselor consultation: Skills for working effectively with parents, teachers, and other school personnel*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Brosch, T. (2021). Affect and emotions as drivers of climate change perception and action: a review. *Current Opinion in Behavioral Sciences*, 42, 15-21.
- Cheema, I. U., BiBi, B., Iqbal, M., & Fareha, Z. (2021). A Comparative Analysis Of Textbook And Activity Based Method In The Subject Of Science At Elementary Level. *Harf-o-Sukhan*, 5(2), 87-96.
- Filliettaz, L., Garcia, S., & Zogmal, M. (2022). Video-based interaction analysis: A research and training method to understand workplace learning and professional development. In *Methods for researching professional learning and development: Challenges, applications and empirical illustrations* (pp. 419-440). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Gilboy, M. S., G. (2015). Enhancing student engagement using the flipped classroom. *Journal of nutrition education and behavior*, 47(1), 109-114.
- Gupta, R., & Prakash, M. (2021). The Role of Textbooks in Enhancing Learning and Knowledge Retention: A Study in Indian Schools. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 82, 102-115.
- Helm, J. H., Katz, L. G., & Wilson, R. (2023). *Young investigators: The project approach in the early years*. Teachers College Press.
- Henze, I., & Barendsen, E. (2019). Unravelling student science teachers' pPCK development and the influence of personal factors using authentic data sources. *Repositioning pedagogical content knowledge in teachers' knowledge for teaching science*, 203-223.
- Jeyaraj, J. S. (2019). Traditional learning vs. experiential learning. *American College Journal of English Language and Literature (ACJELL)*, 9, 43-46.
- Lawson, M. A., (2020). Comparing fast thinking and slow thinking: The relative benefits of interventions, individual differences, and inferential rules. *Judgment and Decision making*, 15(5), 660-684.
- Lewis, M., & Williams, C. (2022). Experiential Learning in the Classroom: Theory and Practice for Teaching Demonstrations. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 113(5), 872-890.
- Mastropieri, M. A., & Scruggs, T. E. (2020). *The Inclusive Classroom: Strategies for Effective Differentiated Instruction*. Pearson Education.
- Misra, P. (2018). MOOCs for teacher professional development: Reflections and suggested actions. *Open Praxis*, 10(1), 67-77.
- Morgan, B., & Rabie, S. (2019). Using interests and Holland's model of vocational personality types in career counselling: Some thoughts and research findings. *Handbook of innovative career counselling*, 485-503.
- NNADI, G. C., (2021). Menace Of Sexual Violence And Abuses Against Women And The Girl-Child In Nigeria: The Role Of Counselling In Trauma Healing.
- Noordin, M. F., & Risanty, R. D. (2021, February). Eclectic approach as idea of e-Edu counseling preliminary system model. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1764, No. 1, p. 012045). IOP Publishing.
- Pandey, S. R., & Sharma, M. R. (2022). Mentoring and Professional Development: A Gateway to Professionalism. *Journal of Social Work and Science Education*, 3(2), 168-178.
- Rasmitadila, R., Aliyyah, R. R., Rachmadtullah, R., Samsudin, A., Syaodih, E., Nurtanto, M., & Tambunan, A. R. S. (2020). The perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning

- during the COVID-19 pandemic period. *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies*, 7(2), 90-109.
- Rogers, C. R. (2019). *Client-Centered Therapy: Its Current Practice, Implications, and Theory*. Houghton Mifflin Harcourt.
- Salendab, F. (2023). Proposed Instructional Scheme in the New Normal Education: Basis for Pedagogical Strategies/Practices. *Psychology and Education*
- Sanders, L., & Hill, P. (2020). The Effectiveness of Directive Counseling in Enhancing Decision-Making Skills in University Students. *Counseling Psychologist*, 48(6), 832-850.
- Schmidt, H. G., Wagener, S. L., Smeets, G. A., Keemink, L. M., & van Der Molen, H. T. (2015). On the use and misuse of lectures in higher education. *Health Professions Education*, 1(1), 12-18.
- Simmons, O. E. (2022). Experiencing grounded theory: A comprehensive guide to learning, Assisted Learning, 38(4), 1160-117
- Solehuddin, M. U. H. A. M. M. A. D., Muktiarni, M., Rahayu, N. I., & Maryanti, R. (2023). Counseling guidance in science education: Definition, literature review, and bibliometric analysis. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 18, 1-13.
- Subramani, P. N., & Iyappan, V. (2018). Innovative methods of teaching and learning. *Journal of applied and advanced research*, 3(1), 20
- Surur, M., Ridhwan, M., Azis, A. A., & Noervadila, I. (2023). Improving Creative Thinking Skills of Early Childhood by Utilizing Robotic Activities in Learning Process. *Journal of Childhood Development*, 3(1), 79-83.
- Sutanti, N. (2019). Exploring the challenges of the non-directive attitude in person-centered counselling in Indonesian culture. *KnE Social Sciences*, 37-50.
- Tapp, L. M. (2022). Learning Science: Techniques for Better Certification Exam Results. *Professional Safety*, 67(12), 16-21.
- Tatar, A. E., (2020). Prediction of academic performance at undergraduate graduation: Course grades or grade point average? *Applied sciences*, 10(14), 4967.
- Tight, M. (2020). Student retention and engagement in higher education. *Journal of further and Higher Education*, 44(5), 689-704.
- Van Wermeskerken, M., & Van Gog, T. (2017). Seeing the instructor's face and gaze in demonstration video examples affects attention allocation but not learning. *Computers & Education*, 113, 98-107.
- Walsh, A., & Gann, S. M. (2020). Group Counseling in Institutional Settings. *Correctional Assessment, Casework, and Counseling*, 199-223.
- Wharton, E., & Walsler, R. D. (2019). Acceptance-based interventions in the treatment of PTSD: Group and individual pilot data using Acceptance and Commitment Therapy. *Journal of Contextual Behavioral Science*, 14, 55-64
- Zhang, H., Su, S., Zeng, Y., & Lam, J. F. (2022). An experimental study on the effectiveness of students' learning in scientific courses through constructive alignment—a case study from an MIS course. *Education Sciences*, 12(5), 338.